

STRATEGIC ASSET MANAGEMENT AND CORPORATE EFFICIENCY IN THE NIGERIAN MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY

Adeyemi Oluwaseun David

Department of Accounting, Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20155162>

ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>The main focus of any firm is to maximize the wealth of its owners and this will happen when sustainability is guaranteed. This is the core objective of asset replacement model that stipulates the replacement of an asset when its productive capacity is on the decline. In other to test the relevance of this model in the light of the contemporary world of commerce, this study examined asset management and performance of quoted manufacturing companies in line with asset replacement model. Panel data were used for the study and ten years financial statement from 2011 to 2020 of three well established manufacturing companies were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study found out that all the parameters postulated by asset replacement model are still very credible in the present day operations of manufacturing companies and therefore is still very useful. The study concluded that asset replacement model is still very relevant in this contemporary world of commerce.</p>	<p>Asset Replacement, Maintenance Cost, Performance, Running Cost, Panel data.</p>

Introduction

The key objective of any firm is to maximize the owners' wealth as well as to meet the needs of other stakeholders who want to rely on the financial information for decision –making. A lot of factors could be held responsible for the growth and development of business ventures especially as it concerns performance and wealth maximization. Internal factors like style of operations coined out at the policymaking hierarchy of the business, management of assets in such a way as to bring about optimal utilization. Also remuneration and incentive packages for the members of staff are sine qua non to the growth of the organization. External factors cannot be brushed aside since no business organization operates in a vacuum. The environment in which the business operates may seem to have high degree of financial performance but may be finding it difficult managing their assets efficiently. This assertion is corroborated by Liargovas & Skandalis (2008) through their submission that one of the key factors affecting financial performance of businesses is asset management. Efficiency in the management of assets is therefore, a crucial factor in boosting the financial performance of manufacturing firms that will eventually bring about tremendous contribution to the general growth of the economy. According to Schreiberfeder (2004), the way an organization controls and manages its various assets may have the greatest

potential for improving the organization's value. One of the strategies for managing the assets of firm is provided by the Asset Replacement Model. This model is an operation research technique that stipulates the appropriate period to replace an asset based on some welldefined parameters. This model is a decision-making model that justifies the replacement of an asset at a point in time when the asset starts declining in its efficiency and therefore uneconomical to run. This, according to the model is absolutely necessary if the firm wants to sustain or even improve on its current level of performance. Asset replacement model takes into consideration

- i. The maintenance cost of the asset
- ii. The running cost and
- iii. The scrap value.

The inter-relationship of these three parameters, according to asset replacement model, dictates the period the asset should be replaced. In this wise, the model stipulates that as the asset is being used, the maintenance and running costs increase and at the same time the scrap value decreases. The relevance of this model to asset management and performance of firms in the manufacturing sector forms the crux of this study. The study was therefore carried out to examine the asset management and performance of quoted manufacturing companies in the context of asset replacement model.

Conceptual Review

- Asset Replacement Model

Asset replacement theory in operations research is a model on decisions making based asset on the appropriate time to replace any asset with another new asset in order to sustain or even improve on the level of performance of businesses. The replacement theory is useful in situations categorized as follows:

- i. Items that deteriorates with time e.g Motor Vehicle.
- ii. Assets that is outdated due to new technology coming up e.g computer package.
- iii. Items which fail completely with use and not because of deterioration. Examples are electronic parts, bulbs etc.
- iv. Asset that fails to meet the current capacity of the business.

- Asset Management

Assets are defined as “resources controlled by an entity as a result of past events and from which future economic benefits are expected to flow to the entity” (Mawih, 2014). Assets are of two types, tangible and intangible. Tangible assets are made up of Non-current assets and Current asset, which according to Mawih (2014), are mostly presented in the statement of financial position. In the opinion of Hastings (2010), physical assets are referred to as items such as machinery, vehicles, plants, building etc. which are used to carry out business functions. Current assets on the other hand, are assets used in the day to day running of the business and these include inventories, receivables, bank and cash even prepayments. Both non-current and current assets are made use of in carrying out the operations of the business and consequently in generation wealth for the owners of the business. Asset management is about how the assets of companies are managed to yield maximally to the performance of the business. Adequate management of physical assets is so key that leads towards the achievement of organizational goals and objectives of the business.

According to Wenzler (2005), asset management of a business entails a process of identification, design, construction, operation and maintenance of physical assets. Management of assets are so germane because this will in the long run determine the success or otherwise of the business. The primary aim of physical asset management is the effective use of physical assets across their lifecycles. Assets invested in the business should

not too be excessive or low but must be commensurate to the level of operation of that business to result in the generation or reasonable profit eventually. Every organization proffers strategy of managing its physical assets (Charles & Brent, 2005).

The measurement for assets management and utilization is return on assets (ROA) which indicates the rate at which assets are contributing to the overall wealth of the business. This is also called asset efficiency. According to Warrad & Omari (2015), asset efficiency is a ratio that determines the efficiency of managing all the company's assets. This efficiency ratio indicates the contributions of assets as a result of good management and utilization. Enekwe (2015) considered efficiency ratio as turnover ratio which measures the efficiency of the use of the capital invested in the assets by relating the main naira volume of sales to the total assets employed in the business.

Parameters for Managing Assets in line with Assets

Replacement Model

The strategy for asset management according to asset replacement model bothers on some three key parameters:

- i. The cost of maintenance of the asset.
- ii. The running cost of the asset.
- iii. The scrap value which determines the depreciation level.

The asset replacement model postulates that any asset in use should be replaced when the asset is not contributing reasonably to the overall profit or growth of the business. If the asset is not replaced at the right time, the business will gradually be declining in operational capacity.

Concept of Financial Performance

This is a concept with several connotations and therefore there are varieties of definitions attributed to the concept of performance due to its subjective nature Performance is construed by some scholars as the achievement of the set objectives. Noye (2002) believed that performance is achieving the goals that were set in convergence of enterprise orientations. In his submission, performance is not a mere achieving of an outcome but rather it is the result of a comparison between the outcome and the objective. Financial performance of manufacturing companies will be viewed in this study as having a reasonable return on the assets (ROA) employed through the efficient management of assets. This is the focus of asset replacement theory.

Theoretical Framework

System theory

System theory has a long history of existence in the area of human knowledge. Shahid (2016) pointed out that some scholars traced the development of system theory back to Aristotle. There are two versions of the system theory. The first, called closed systems came out of classical physics developed by Norbert Wiener and Ross Ashby in 1949. The other called open systems approach comes from a biologist named Ludwig Von Bertalanaffy in 1973, who used the term general systems theory to describe some biological phenomena and to distinguish them from closed systems.

This study will therefore focus on the open systems as manufacturing firms cannot grow and survive without interacting with their environments. Systems theory describes the relations between the parts because the behaviour of the system is therefore dependent on the properties of the elements. The systems theory has a significant effect on management of assets and understanding of organization's operations. A manufacturing system can be seen as a collection of different assets unified to accomplish an overall goal of profit maximization. If one part of the system is removed, the nature of the system is changed as well.

The relevance of systems theory in this study is that it helps managers to look at the assets management more broadly by enabling them to recognize the various forms of assets and in particular, the interactions of the parts.

Empirical Review

A number of studies have been carried out on the area of asset management and asset efficiency.

Mawih (2014) carried out a study on the effects of assets structure (non-current assets and current assets) on the financial performance of some manufacturing companies listed on Muscat Securities Market, using the content analysis of annual reports of a sample of 28 out of 70 (40%) companies for the period 2008-2012. The assets structure was measured by non-current asset turnover and current asset turnover while the financial performance was measured by return on assets and return on equity. The study used two main hypotheses. The first one examined the effects of total assets turnover on ROE. The second overall result for the study revealed that the structure of assets does not have a strong impact on profitability in terms of ROA. The result also indicates that only the noncurrent assets have impact on profitability in terms of ROE unlike ROA.

Jamah & Asadi (2012) studied the relationship between assets management efficiency and profitability of 13 auto manufacturing companies listed on the Bombay Stock Exchange for the period 2006-2010. The assets turnover was one of the ratios used in measuring the assets management efficiency. The findings showed that there is a high degree of correlation between profitability and asset management efficiency.

Azadi (2013) examined the effects of changes in assets (non-current and current) on operating earnings of manufacturing companies listed on the Stock Exchange Market. The study used Ordinary Least Square (OLS) to investigate these effects. Results show that, for food and metal industries, non-current assets have positive and significant effect on the operating earnings and for chemical industries, current assets do not have a significant positive effect on operating earnings.

Okwo, Ugwunta and Nweze (2012) assessed the impact of a company's investment in non-current assets on its operating profit margin. The study obtained data from the financial statements of the sampled companies operating in the Nigerian Breweries sector for a period from 1999-2009. The data were analysed using regression statistical method. The study indicates that there is a non-statistically significant positive relationship between investment in non-current assets and operating profit. The study did not show any strong positive impact of investment in noncurrent assets on the operating profit of brewery firms in Nigeria.

None of the reviewed literature specifically focused on assets management and financial performance of quoted manufacturing with respect to the replacement of asset theory and hence the gap created for this study.

The study covered the period of 2011-2020. For the purpose of this study, Return on Assets (ROA) was used as proxy for performance. To determine the replacement cycle, depreciation Policy was adopted, maintenance policy that included insurance cost was used and the running cost incurred was also considered. All these were picked from the financial statements of the selected quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives

The study aimed at assessing the relevance of asset replacement model in asset management and performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. While the objectives are to:

1. Determine the relationship between asset replacement cycle and performance of quoted manufacturing companies.
2. Evaluate the impact of asset maintenance policy.
3. Examine the effect of running cost of asset on performance of manufacturing companies.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: Asset replacement cycle has no significant relationship with performance of quoted manufacturing companies.

H02: Asset maintenance policy has no significant impact on performance of quoted manufacturing companies.

H03: Running cost of asset has no significant effect performance of quoted manufacturing companies.

Methodology

The research design for this study is Ex post facto and the population of study is all the quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria as at 31st May, 2021. Convenience sampling technique was used in the selection of three manufacturing companies for the study and in selecting the sample size because of the difficulty encountered in getting the financial statements of companies in this sector. The companies selected were Nigerian Breweries, Cadbury and Nestle. The study used secondary data from financial statements of the sampled manufacturing companies from 2010 -2019 financial statements. Trend analysis was employed to analyse the data for estimating Descriptive and inferential statistics.

Measurement of variables

Dependent Variable (Financial Performance) The dependent variable of the study is firms’ financial performance measured by Return on Assets (ROA).

Independent variable

With regards to independent variables, replacement cycle is measured by the depreciation policy of the manufacturing companies chosen. The maintenance and running costs will be measured by ratio of maintenance cost to the assets value.

Model Specification

In trying to achieve the objectives of this study, a regression model was formulated to ascertain the relationship between the parameters: including relationship between asset replacement cycle and performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e \text{ ----- Eq. 1 ROA} = f(\text{DP, MC, and RC}) \text{ -----}$$

Eq. 2 Where:

ROA (Y) = Return on Assets (Dependent variable); a proxy for financial performance of the quoted companies.

DP (X₁) = Depreciation policy (independent variable) (if depreciation policy is reported in the annual financial statement, 1, if not, 0)

MC (X₂) = Maintenance cost (Independent variable): Expressed as percentage of ratio of repairs and maintenance cost: Total Assets X100%

And RC (X₃) =Running Cost (Independent variable): Expressed as percentage of ratio of production cost: Total Assets X100%

Functional Relationship

$$\text{ROA} = f(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{DP} + e) \text{F1.....Eq.3 ROA} = f(\beta_0 + \beta_2 \text{MC} + e) \text{F2.....Eq.4}$$

$$\text{ROA} = f(\beta_0 + \beta_3 \text{RC} + e) \text{F3.....Eq.5}$$

F1, F2 and F3 are the working functional relationships that would be used to ascertain the relationship between asset replacement cycle and performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria; viz; Nigerian Breweries, Nestle Plc and Cadbury Plc.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Data analysis was done with the aid of the E-view econometric software and secondary data ranging from 2010-2019 were used to establish relationship between asset replacement cycle and performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The relationship between Depreciation policy (DP), Maintenance cost (%)

and Running cost on the financial performance of the three quoted firms: Nigerian Breweries, Nestle Plc and Cadbury Plc were examined.

Trend analysis

ROA

Fig. 1: Trend analysis of the ROA across the manufacturing

Fig. 3: Trend analysis of the MC% across the manufacturing companies from 2010-2019.

Fig. 4: Trend analysis of the RC% across the manufacturing companies from 2010-2019.

Companies from 2010-2019.

The Fig.1 above shows ROA range of about -5% to 33% which depicts fluctuations of financial profit and loss among the manufacturing companies across the years Nestle Plc especially in 2019. Other companies recorded relatively high returns, but none had a peak higher than Nestle in 2019.

Under review. A relatively higher ROA were recorded in

Fig.2: Trend analysis of the DP across the manufacturing companies from 2010-2019.

The Fig.2 above showed DP range of 0 to 1 which depicts inconsistencies in reports of depreciation policies across the years under review. However, except for Nigerian breweries in 2011 and 2012 other manufacturing companies stated their depreciation policies across the years.

2019.

The Fig.3 below showed a relatively higher maintenance cost recorded in Nigerian Breweries especially between 2016 and 2019. This may be due to non-replacement of their assets in good time. Other companies recorded relatively low maintenance costs but none had a peak higher than Nigerian Breweries for 2016 and

The Fig.4 above showed RC% range of about 0% to 45% in relative to Total Assets which depicts fluctuations of running cost among the manufacturing companies across the years under review. A relatively higher RC% were recorded in Cadbury Plc especially in 2015-2016 which is about 40%. Other companies recorded relatively high Running cost, but none had a peak higher than Cadbury plc

Descriptive analysis

2015-2016. this high running cost may be as a result of delay in the replacement of assets in these companies

Table 1 Descriptive analysis of the dependent and independent variables

ROA	DP		MC_	RC_
Mean	16.73991	0.833333	8.164191	15.22537
Median	16.18426	1.000000	0.316828	4.577595
Maximum	36.81000	1.000000	81.93448	41.84911
Minimum	-1.981309	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Std. Dev.	10.50039	0.379049	20.33603	15.48633
Skewness	0.160232	-1.788854	3.285846	0.453225
Kurtosis	2.129001	4.200000	12.23626	1.373006
Jarque-Bera	1.076669	17.80000	160.6195	4.335952
Probability	0.583720	0.000136	0.000000	0.114409
Sum	502.1974	25.00000	244.9257	456.7612
Sum Sq. Dev.		3197.485	4.166667	11993.07
Observations	30	30	30	30

Source: E-view Output, 2022

ROA	DP		MC%	RC%
ROA	1	-0.103970	-0.296782	0.516244
DP	-0.103970	1	0.103476	0.339633
MC_%	-0.296782	0.103476	1	-0.229350
RC_%	0.516244	0.339633	-0.229350	1

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	17.93381	3.45E-15	5.19E+15	0.00001
DP	-7.990366	4.06E-15	-1.97E+15	0.00001
MC_	-0.068708	7.31E-17	-9.40E+14	0.00001
RC_	0.395766	1.01E-16	3.90E+15	0.00001
ECM	1.000000	1.70E-16	5.87E+15	0.00001
R-squared	1.000000	Mean dependent v ar		16.73991
Adjusted R-squared	1.000000	S.D. dependent var		10.50039
S.E. of regression	7.63E-15	Akaike info criterion		-62.02322
Sum squared resid	1.46E-27	Schwarz criterion		-61.78968
Log likelihood	935.3483	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-61.94851
F-statistic	1.37E+31	Durbin-Watson stat		1.242819
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: E-view Output, 2022

The above correlation analysis shows that RC% are positively related to financial performance (ROA) with the magnitude of 0.516244. Meanwhile DP and MC% are negatively related to ROA with the magnitude of 0.103970 and -0.296782 respectively. However, the strength of the relationship for DP and MC% are weak negative relationship, but RC% had a strong positive

Table 3 Linear Regression of variables relationship. An indication that ROA has a direct relationship with running cost (RC %) than other variables measured.

Linear Regression (Using Error Correction Model) Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) offering the Possibility of revealing information about both the short-run and long-run relationship.

Dependent Variable: ROA

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 07/20/21 Time: 14:19

Sample: 2010 2019

Periods included: 10

Cross-sections included: 3

Total panel (balanced) observations: 30

Source: E-view Output, 2022

The result from the Table 3 above showed that constant of the ECM model is significant (p=0.0001), that is, there is a short term and long-term relationship of the variables employed in this study. The Durbin-Watson statistics value of 1.24 indicates that slight autocorrelation in the model, this may be as a result of relativity of the variables to Total Assets.

Hypothesis I

H₀₁: Asset replacement cycle has no significant relationship with performance of quoted manufacturing companies.

H₁₁: Asset replacement cycle has significant relationship with performance of quoted manufacturing companies.

Inference: From the table 3 above, it can be established that asset replacement cycle has significant ($p=0.0001$) impact on performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Hence, reject the null hypothesis.

Hypothesis 2

H₀₂: Asset maintenance policy has no significant impact on performance of quoted manufacturing companies.

H₁₂: Asset maintenance policy has significant impact on performance of quoted manufacturing companies.

Inference: Asset maintenance policy have significant effect ($p=0.0001$) on performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Hence reject null hypothesis.

Hypothesis 3

H₀₃: Running cost of asset has no significant effect performance of quoted manufacturing companies.

H₁₃: Running cost of asset has significant effect performance of quoted manufacturing companies.

Inference: There is significant relationship ($p=0.0001$) between running cost of asset and performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria in answering the research questions below;

General Comment

Examining the result from the correlation and linear regression, $r = -0.103970$ (with negative coefficient in regression) it shows that there is an indirect relationship between asset replacement lifecycle and the performance of the quoted manufacturing companies. This implied that as the asset replacement cycle get longer, it leads to poor financial performance by 10% annually. The impact of the asset maintenance policy as observed in the regression table, is indirect and significant ($t = -1.97 \times 10^{15}$). ($p=0.0001$) on the financial performance. This implied that as long as asset replacement policy is not kept, the effect will lead to poor financial performance and vice versa. Hence, the policy of asset maintenance is still much relevant to the current manufacturing companies. The running cost has a positive relationship/ effect on the performance of the quoted manufacturing companies. This is deduced from the table 4.2, correlation table, $r = 0.516244$ and table 4.3, regression table, ($t=3.50 \times 10^{15}$). This implied that running cost has direct and positive effect on the performance of the companies. On the other hand, the maintenance cost, especially for companies where replacement policy is not observed, has indirect and a negative effect on the performance of the companies. $r = 0.296782$, ($t = -9.40 \times 10^{15}$).

Conclusion

From the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that asset replacement model still has much relevance in the management of assets in the contemporary world of commerce. Companies can get into serious operational problem if their assets are not replaced at reasonable period because this will cause their production capacity to decline and eventually rob them of the opportunity to maintain or even improve on their profitability. This can have a terrible effect on sustainability of such companies and therefore leading to liquidation problems

References

- Rahimi, K. (2013). Asset Structure Changes and Operating Earnings: Evidence from Tehran Stock Exchange. Trends in Advanced Science and Engineering, 7(1), 30–34.
- Thompson, A. S. & Walker, B. A. (2005). Asset Life Cycle Management and Physical Asset Performance in Process Industries. International Journal of Operations and Production Management, 25(6), 566–579.

- Okeke, C. I. (2015). Financial Ratio Analysis and Corporate Profitability Nexus. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Financial Research*, 3(2), 17–34.
- Morgan, N. (2010). *Principles of Physical Asset Management*. Springer Publications.
- Patel, A. D. & Sharma, R. (2012). Management Efficiency and Profitability in Automobile Industries: Theory and Practice. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 5(5), 2279–2781.
- Demetriou, P. & Karras, S. (2008). *Determinants of Firm Financial Performance: Evidence from Greece*. Athens: Peloponnese Academic Press.
- Al-Farsi, K. A. (2014). Asset Structure and Financial Performance: Evidence from Oman. *Journal of US–China Public Administration*, 11(2), 170–179.
- Peterson, I. (2002). Organizational Performance: Conceptual Clarifications. *Annals of Economic Studies*, 4.
- Nwoye, I. M., Okafor, D. O. & Eze, A. U. (2012). Fixed Asset Investment and Firm Profitability in Nigeria's Brewery Industry. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 4(20), 10–17.
- Schneider, J. (2004). *Inventory Management: Strategies for Profit Maximization*. Microsoft Dynamics Press.
- Al-Hassan, L. & Kareem, R. (2015). Turnover Ratios and Service Sector Performance in Jordan. *Journal of Modern Accounting and Auditing*, 11(2), 77–85.
- Benson, I. (2005). Asset Management Strategy Development in Utility Firms: A Simulation Approach. *Simulation and Gaming*, 36(1), 75–90.
- Khan, A. (2016). *Systems Theory and Management Control*. Retrieved November 20, 2019.